

Empirical Study Of Correlation Between Mutation Score And Model Inference Based Test Suite Adequacy Assessment*

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we investigate a method for test suite evaluation that is based on an inferred model from the test suite. The idea is to use the similarity between the inferred model and the system under test as a measure of test suite adequacy, which is the ability of a test suite to expose errors in the system under test. We define similarity using the root mean squared error computed from the differences of the system under test output and the model output for certain inputs not used for model inference. In the paper we introduce the approach and provide results of an experimental evaluation where we compare the similarity with the mutation score. We used the Pearson Correlation coefficient to calculate whether a linear correlation between mutation score and root mean squared error exists. As a result we obtain that in certain cases the computed similarity strongly correlates with the mutation score.

CCS Concepts

•**Computer systems organization** → *Embedded software*;
•**Computing methodologies** → *Classification and regression trees*; •**Software and its engineering** → *Software testing and debugging*;

Keywords

Software test, Machine learning, Mutation score

1. INTRODUCTION

When testing programs or systems in practice the question when to stop testing naturally arises. To answer this question, it is significant to assess the quality of the underlying test suite in terms of its adequacy with respect to extract faults for a particular program or system under test

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(SUT). In testing practice we are either using certain coverage criteria or mutation score that a test suite has to ensure to serve this purpose. Where coverage gives an indication whether a test suite causes the execution of certain parts of the system under test, alone or in combination, mutation score is a measure for the fault detection capabilities of a test suite directly. Measuring coverage causes a small computational overhead during execution, whereas the mutation score requires the execution of a certain amount of program variants, i.e., the mutants. Therefore, computing the mutation score might be too time consuming in practice.

In this paper, we follow an alternative approach for assuring the fault detection capabilities of test suites. The approach is based on machine learning. The underlying idea is to extract a model of the SUT from the test suite and to compare the obtained model with the original program or system. In case both the model and the SUT are equivalent or very similar, it is evident that the test suite captures the behavior of the SUT in sufficient detail. Otherwise, there are test cases missing in the test suite. The question now is whether the difference between the learned model and the SUT is a good measure for assuring test suite quality? To give an answer to this question, we carried out an experimental evaluation that is based on one specific setting.

The setting comprises a set of Java programs together with a corresponding test suite from which we learn decision trees. Checking program equivalence is an undecidable problem of computer science in general. However, in order to check for equivalence or at least to establish reasons about equivalence or similarity of programs, someone might use statistical methods. When taking a sufficient number of test inputs and executing both, the program and the potentially equivalent program, leads to always the same output, the evidence of equivalence raises. We make use of the same idea to define similarity as a measure based on behavioral differences when applying a random set of test cases to both, the model and the SUT. To measure the behavioral differences we make use of the root mean squared error between the outputs of the model and the SUT for the tests.

In order to judge whether the model inferred from the test suite can be a measure for the fault detection capabilities, the carried out experimental evaluation compares the mutation score of the test suite with the similarity between the inferred model and the test suite. In case both measures correlate, model inference and mutation score can be assumed as equivalent approaches for assuring fault detection capabilities of test suites. The contributions of the paper are as follows:

- Introduction of an alternative approach for test suite adequacy assessment based on machine learning, where we infer a model from the test suite and compute the similarity between the model and the SUT.
- An experimental evaluation of the model inference approach in order to answer the question whether model similarity and mutation score are equally good in assuring fault detection capabilities of test suites.

The paper is organized as follows: In the next section, we introduce the preliminaries and basic definitions as well as the model inference approach. Afterwards, we discuss the experimental evaluation and the obtained results in detail. The paper ends up with a section on related research and the conclusions.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Software testing requires a method to determine when sufficient testing has been done. Such a method can be an adequacy criterion for a test suite, where the adequacy criterion should reflect the ability of the test suite to expose errors in the SUT. The renowned mutation score and a novel model inference based assessment method are two test suite adequacy criteria. To determine whether a linear correlation exists between these two adequacy criteria, we calculate the Pearson Correlation coefficient.

2.1 Mutation Score

The mutation score is the result of mutation testing. Mutation testing [6] is a fault-based testing technique where modifications of the SUT lead to faulty versions of the SUT. These faulty versions are called mutants. A mutant is said to be a killed mutant, if a test suite can distinguish the mutant from the original program. Mutation score is defined as:

DEFINITION 1 (MUTATION SCORE). *Mutation score μ is the proportion between killed mutants k and the number of existing mutants n .*

$$\mu = \frac{k}{n} \quad \square$$

In this work we used mutants for Java source code from the following categories, which are described in detail in [8]:

- Operator Replacement Binary (ORB): Replace all occurrences of arithmetic (AOR), logical (LOR), shift (SOR), conditional (COR), and relational (ROR) operators with all valid alternatives.
- Literal Value Replacement (LVR): Force literals to take a positive value, a negative value, and zero. Additionally, all reference initializations are replaced by null.

Mutation score is in $[0,1]$. We assess a test suite to be of maximum adequacy if the mutation score is 1 and a test suite to be inadequate if the mutation score is 0.

2.2 Model Inference Based Adequacy Assessment

In this work we infer a model from a test suite by learning a decision tree. As shown in Figure 1 we need a test suite TS which is divided into two distinct subsets TS_{equiv} and TS_{dt} . For the empirical evaluation we decided to use a relative size ratio of 9:1 for subsets TS_{equiv} and TS_{dt} respectively. The

Figure 1: Schema of model inference based quality assessment.

test suite for which we assess its adequacy is TS_{dt} . Therefore we infer a model from TS_{dt} . The second subset TS_{equiv} is used to assess the adequacy by comparing the outcomes from the SUT and from the inferred model when executing the test suite. If all outcomes are equivalent, we assess a test suite TS_{dt} to be adequate. If different outcomes appear from the SUT and the inferred model when executing the same test case from TS_{equiv} , we calculate the root mean squared error to assess the adequacy defined as follows:

DEFINITION 2 (ROOT MEAN SQUARED ERROR). *The root mean squared error $rmse$ measures the differences from the outcomes of an SUT and a decision tree of n test cases.*

$$rmse = \sqrt{\frac{(p_1 - a_1)^2 + \dots + (p_n - a_n)^2}{n}}$$

p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n are the outcomes from the inferred model
 a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are the outcomes from the SUT \square

The root mean squared error is in $[0,1]$ where 0 indicates maximum adequacy and 1 indicates an inadequate test suite. If the outcomes of the learned decision tree and the SUT are different for the i th test case, the difference of $(p_i - a_i)$ depends on the number of different categories the decision tree and the SUT categorize and on possible misclassifications while learning the decision tree. The difference of $(p_i - a_i)$ is

$$(p_i - a_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{\#\text{categories}} & \text{if no misclassifications exist,} \\ \frac{P(p_i|leaf)}{\#\text{categories}} & \text{if misclassifications exist,} \\ 0 & \text{if } p_i \text{ equals } a_i. \end{cases}$$

Wrongly classified, or misclassified test cases cause probability distributions $P(p_i|leaf)$ for the classified test cases at the leaf nodes. This probability distribution affects the root mean squared error, but depends on the number of misclassifications and is calculated for each learned decision tree individually.

The decision tree learning method we used in this work was the C4.5 algorithm as introduced in [13]. In real world applications only a test suite TS_{dt} exists, which requires in addition to create a set TS_{equiv} to assess the adequacy of TS_{dt} .

2.3 Pearson Correlation

In this work we investigate whether a relationship between mutation score and a model inference based adequacy assessment exists. To quantify this relationship we calculate the Pearson Correlation coefficient [12] between mutation

Table 1: Strength interpretations of the Pearson Correlation coefficient r

r	strength
0.00-0.19	very weak
0.20-0.39	weak
0.40-0.59	moderate
0.60-0.79	strong
0.80-1.0	very strong

score and the root mean squared error of the model inference based assessment. The Pearson Correlation coefficient indicates the extent to which two variables have a linear relationship and is defined as:

DEFINITION 3 (PEARSON CORRELATION COEFFICIENT).

The Pearson Correlation coefficient r measures the linear correlation between two variables.

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

n is the number of test cases,

x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are the results for the root mean squared error of TS_{dt} ,

y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n are the results for the mutation score of TS_{dt} ,
 \bar{x} is the sample mean for x_1, \dots, x_n (and analogously for \bar{y})

□

The resulting Pearson Correlation coefficient is in $[-1,1]$. The linear relationship is indicated by the direction (sign +/-) and the strength of r . According to Evans [1] the result for the Pearson Correlation coefficient can be interpreted in strength by the value of r as shown in Table 1.

When interpreting the Pearson Correlation coefficient a value of $r = 0$ indicates no correlation, a value $r < 0$ indicates negative correlation, and a value $r > 0$ indicates positive correlation.

For the empirical evaluation we created a sample of 100 test suites TS_{dt} where all test suites in the sample have the same size. The test cases for TS_{dt} are selected randomly. For each member of the sample we calculated mutation score and the root mean squared error.

To obtain a reasonable result from the calculation of the Pearson Correlation coefficient, the data should be sampled from populations with normal distributions. To test whether the 100 mutation score results and the 100 root mean squared error results for each example are normally distributed, we used the Shapiro-Wilk test [14]. From the Shapiro-Wilk test we conclude that our input data to calculate the Pearson Correlation coefficient most likely come from a normally distributed population.

Since we assume that a growing mutation score indicates a reduction of the root mean squared error, we expect the Pearson Correlation coefficient to be the right tool to confirm this assumption.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For the empirical evaluation of the Pearson Correlation coefficient between mutation score and root mean squared error we used six example programs and their corresponding test suites. As depicted in Figure 1 we divided the given

test suite TS of each program into a subset $TS_{dt} \subset TS$ and a subset $TS_{equiv} \subset TS$. We take TS_{dt} as the test suite for which adequacy is assessed on the one hand by mutation score and on the other hand by model inference. To obtain the mutation score we have to execute the test cases in TS_{dt} for each mutant. To get the root mean squared error an additional set of test cases TS_{equiv} is required, but these additional test cases have to be executed only once. We presume that all test cases in TS pass if they would be executed on the original SUT.

3.1 Examples

For the experimental evaluation we make use of six Java programs:

1. TCAS: For the traffic collision avoidance system (TCAS) an implementation in C with a test suite and mutants can be found in [17]. Here we use a Java implementation. Also the mutants were translated into Java.
2. BMI: The body mass index (BMI) example is a program that categorizes a person by means of weight and height into one of five different categories. For this example we used the source code published in [2].
3. Triangle: The triangle example program [4] determines whether the inputs correspond to a valid triangle and if so, whether the valid triangle is equilateral, scalene, or isosceles.
4. POP3: The POP3 example is a state machine. A graphical representation of the implemented state machine is shown in Figure 2.
5. CAS: The car alarm system (CAS) example is a state machine. A graphical representation of the implemented state machine is shown in Figure 3.
6. UTF8: The Guava UTF8 example is a part of Google's Guava library, which checks if an input sequence of bytes is a well formed UTF8 encoded input. The source code of the UTF8 function can be found at [18].

The input types for the examples are either continuous or enumerated, where an enumerated input is limited by a finite number of different values. The outputs for all six examples in this work are categorical.

The examples TCAS, BMI, UTF8 and Triangle appear as single transition functions, without any externally observable states, that process input vectors of continuous type values. The input for the UTF8 example is a vector of four bytes where validity is checked for the input bytes consecutively. Therefore the UTF8 example represents a state machine, without any externally observable states, with transitions after a valid input byte was processed. If the input vector for the UTF8 example contains less than four bytes, the other bytes remain unknown (indicated by '?'). Decision tree learning can be used even when some input values are unknown. Missing input values for decision tree learning are estimated. For estimation either the value that is most common among the test vectors for the input value is used, or probabilities are estimated for the input values. For the four examples, namely TCAS, BMI, Triangle, and UTF8 we consider a test case tc to be a test vector of k input values

Figure 2: State machine showing the POP3 example.

Figure 3: State machine showing the CAS example.

and an expected output value, e.g., $tc = (in_1, \dots, in_k, out)$. For the POP3 and CAS examples a test case is a sequence s of n test vectors, e.g., $s = \langle tc_1, \dots, tc_n \rangle$ where n varies. Each test vector in s consists of four values where the first value is the input value, the second value is the expected outcome after executing the previous test vector, the third value is the current state, and the fourth value is the expected outcome after executing the current test vector. The inputs for the POP3 and the CAS examples are enumerated.

The attributes source lines of code (*SLOC*), number of output categories (*categories*), size of the test suite TS (*#TS*), and number of mutants (*#mutants*) for the six examples are given in Table 2. Despite the mutants for the TCAS example, the mutants for the remaining examples only use a single mutation per mutant. For the TCAS example we used the existing test suite and generated random test cases for the other examples. The size of a test suite is the number of test cases it contains. Table 3 displays different properties for TS, the learned decision tree from TS, and the control flow graphs for the six examples. The least number of inputs (k) is two for the BMI example and the maximum is 12 for

Table 2: Attributes *SLOC* (source lines of code), size of the test suite *TS*, and number of mutants of the example programs.

Name	<i>SLOC</i>	categories	# <i>TS</i>	#mutants
TCAS	100	3	1,545	41
BMI	19	5	1,000	28
Triangle	30	4	1,000	35
POP3	122	10	1,000	167
CAS	110	5	1,000	167
UTF8	56	2	1,000	147

Table 3: The properties of the initial test suite, the learned tree, and the control flow graph for the 6 examples.

ex.	test suite		learned tree				cfg
	k	n	misc.	size	leaves	len.	size
TCAS	12	1545	0	372	256	12	431
BMI	2	1000	9	107	54	9	67
Trian.	3	1000	246	57	29	14	99
POP3	3	25117	0	165	123	2	695
CAS	3	54437	0	33	28	2	511
UTF8	4	1000	83	33	17	11	229

the TCAS example. As mentioned before k is 3 for POP3 and CAS, which are the input value, the previous expected outcome, and the current state. Because for CAS and POP3 each test case is a sequence of test vectors, the number of test vectors n is much higher than the size of the test suite. For the examples BMI, Triangle, and UTF8 misclassifications (*misc.*) appear even when learning the decision tree from TS. The decision tree with the most nodes is the decision tree for TCAS with a *size* of 372 nodes and 256 *leaves*. Also for TCAS the maximum number of edges which can be counted when traversing the decision tree from the root node to a leaf node is the highest with *len.* 12 whereas *len.* is just 2 for POP3 and CAS. Further we extracted the control flow graphs (cfg) of the six examples and counted the nodes in the graphs where the highest numbers of nodes are given by POP3 and CAS with *size* 695 and 511 respectively.

3.2 Results

As introduced in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 we obtained the values for mutation score and root mean squared error to calculate the Pearson Correlation coefficient for the six examples described in Section 3.1. To calculate the values for the root mean squared error we used the Java library Weka 3.7 [19].

We selected 100 random subsets for TS_{dt} from each of the six example test suites and acquired mutation score and root mean squared error for each of the TS_{dts} .

Figure 4 shows the results for mutation score and root mean squared error for the TCAS example. The Pearson Correlation coefficient for the TCAS example is $r_{TCAS} = 0.22$. The mutation score results are in the interval [0.07, 0.57] and the root mean squared error results are in the interval [0.33, 0.6].

Figure 4: Correlation of mutation score and root mean squared error for the TCAS example.

Figure 6: Correlation of mutation score and root mean squared error for the BMI example.

Figure 5: Correlation of mutation score and root mean squared error for the Triangle example.

Figure 7: Correlation of mutation score and root mean squared error for the UTF8 example.

In Figure 5 the results for the Triangle example are shown. The mutation score results are in the interval $[0.33, 0.78]$ and the root mean squared error results are in the interval $[0.45, 0.65]$. For the Triangle example the Pearson Correlation coefficient is $r_{Triangle} = 0.332$.

For the BMI example the resulting mutation scores and root mean squared errors are shown in Figure 6. The mutation score results are in the interval $[0.17, 0.86]$ and the root mean squared error results are in the interval $[0.32, 0.53]$. The Pearson Correlation coefficient for the BMI example is $r_{BMI} = 0.21$.

The results of mutation score and root mean squared error for the UTF8 example are shown in Figure 7. The mutation score results are in the interval $[0.11, 0.42]$ and the root mean squared error results are in the interval $[0.32, 0.72]$. The resulting Pearson Correlation coefficient for the UTF8 example is $r_{UTF8} = 0.202$.

Figure 8 shows the 100 mutation score and root mean squared error results for the POP3 example. The mutation score results are in the interval $[0.24, 1.0]$ and the root mean squared error results are in the interval $[0.11, 0.22]$. For the POP3 example the Pearson Correlation coefficient is $r_{POP3} = -0.632$.

In Figure 9 the results for the CAS example are shown. The mutation score results are in the interval $[0.1, 0.38]$ and the root mean squared error results are in the interval

Figure 8: Correlation of mutation score and root mean squared error for the POP3 example.

Figure 9: Correlation of mutation score and root mean squared error for the CAS example.

[0.0, 0.12]. For the CAS example the Pearson Correlation coefficient is $r_{CAS} = -0.871$.

The six figures showing the results for mutation score and root mean squared error also contain a trendline each which was created by linear regression as explained in [10]. This trendline supports the visualization of the Pearson Correlation coefficient.

3.3 Evaluation

We interpret the Pearson Correlation coefficients obtained from our results as explained in Table 1. For the examples TCAS, Triangle, BMI, and UTF8 the correlation is weak. The correlation for the POP3 example is strong and for the CAS example the correlation is very strong. The optimal Pearson correlation coefficient, which could indicate that we can use model inference based adequacy assessment instead of mutation score is -1. This follows from the assumption that if the mutation score of a test suite is high, the root mean squared error is low and vice versa.

The examples resulting in a weak correlation indicate that mutation score could not be replaced by model inference based adequacy assessment. To verify this claim we ran two additional experiments for TCAS, Triangle, BMI, and UTF8. First we changed the size ratio of TS_{dt} and TS_{equal} from 1:9 to 1:4, 3:7, 2:3, and 1:1. Second we divided the mutants into categories as explained in Section 2.1 and analyzed whether a correlation between model inference based quality assessment and the mutation score of certain categories of mutants exists.

Changing the sizes of TS_{dt} and TS_{equal} did not affect the Pearson correlation coefficient significantly. We were able to categorize the mutants into the six categories: AOR, LVR, ROR, COR, SOR, and LOR. To obtain the Pearson Correlation coefficient we created again 100 test suites TS_{dt} for each mutant category, for each example, and processed mutation score and root mean squared error.

For the four examples TCAS, Triangle, BMI, and UTF8 no sign of linear correlation was obtained for any category of mutants. The examples POP3 and CAS result in a strong and very strong correlation respectively. This originates from the facts that POP3 and CAS use enumerated inputs and that the test sequences from which the models are inferred contain additionally to the inputs and outputs also information about the current state and the preceding out-

put. As shown in Table 3 the learned decision trees for POP3 and CAS have at most two edges from the root to any leaf node. For all other examples the inputs are continuous values which ranges can be split multiple times while growing a decision tree. The algorithm to learn the decision tree is essential for the obtained results. For examples with continuous types we obtain binary decision trees which split value ranges. For the examples with enumerated input types we obtain decision trees with an outgoing edge from a node for each possible value the variable represented by the node can be assigned to. The sizes of the control flow graphs for POP3 and CAS are highest, but to obtain similar coverage results for all examples also the number of test vectors is highest for these two examples.

4. RELATED WORK

In their recent work Fraser and Walkinshaw [2] answer the question whether there exists a relationship between their adequacy score and the ability of a test suite to detect defects. The authors also use the term adequacy, which was defined in [3] where a test suite is adequate if it implies no errors in the SUT if it executes correctly. In [2] the authors do not obtain a positive correlation at all for their examples with categorical outcomes when using a similar machine learning based test suite adequacy assessment. The approach introduced in this work to assess the adequacy of a test suite by model inference is similar to the idea of probably approximately correct (PAC) learning [15]. PAC provides a theoretical framework for evaluating model accuracy.

The same method of learning a decision tree from a test suite using the C4.5 algorithm is applied by Papadopoulos and Walkinshaw in [11]. In [11] the authors use the decision tree as input model for test case generation to extend an existing test suite.

In [5] the authors demonstrate empirically that there is a low to moderate correlation between coverage and effectiveness of a test suite. To assess effectiveness they also use the mutation score of a test suite. The authors calculate two different correlation coefficients. First they calculate the Pearson Correlation coefficient as we did in this work. Second they calculate the Kendall Correlation coefficient [9], which yields similar results as obtained by the Pearson Correlation coefficient.

Just et al. investigate in [7] whether mutants are a valid substitute for real faults. Their results show a statistically significant correlation between mutant detection and real fault detection, independent of coverage.

In [16] the author introduces a definition of test data adequacy. She points out that if the behavior of a system can be inferred from a test suite, it can be concluded, that the SUT's behavior is adequately tested. She also describes practical limitations, which origin in the fact that equivalence is not decidable. In [20] Zhu et al. review the theories of inductive inference and their relevance to software testing.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We conclude that there can be a linear correlation between mutation score and model inference based test suite adequacy assessment. However, this relationship depends on the data within a test suite and the input types of the SUT. In contrast to related work we added information about the

current state and the previous output of the SUT to each test case in a test suite for certain examples, that resulted in a clear linear correlation.

The examples resulting in a weak positive correlation, are the examples with continuous input types and without information about internal states of an SUT within a test suite. The types of the inputs and the information about internal states within the test suite seem to be the essential reasons why for some examples a linear correlation exists and for some not. We address the open research on the detailed differences of the examples and the test suites in future work.

Generally we obtained results for the root mean squared error of an inferred model with ranges from 0.11 up to 0.4. These results, and the related work, clearly show us, that it is possible to assess the adequacy of a test suite by model inference. In future work we will prepare some real world examples and also investigate whether there exist linear correlations between model inference based test suite adequacy assessment and various coverage assessment methods. Further we will apply different machine learning methods to infer models from a test suite and adopt other similarity measures to assess the approximations of the inferred model and the SUT. From these improvements we will get better insights when to use a model inference based method, which only depends on the inputs and outputs of a program, and when to use test suite adequacy assessment methods, which depend on source code modifications.

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